

Global Stability and Numerical Approach on Three Species Ecology Consisting of Host, Commensal and Neutralism with Limited Resources

N NARESH KUMAR, Y MADHUSUDHAN REDDY, M SIVA TEJA

Assistant Professor ^{1,3}, PROFESSOR ²

nareshkumar729@gmail.com, ymsmadhu@gmail.com, Tejamopuri3@gmail.com

Department of Mathematics, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract: Three hosts—S₂, S₃, and a single commensal—make up the system. In other words, S₁ receives benefits from both hosts without suffering any negative or good effects on its own. Additionally, neither S₂ nor S₃ are biased. At this location, all three species have few resources. Three non-linear simultaneous differential equations of first order make up the model equations. This work uses a properly built Liapunov's function to prove that the system is globally stable. In addition, the Runge-Kutta fourth order approach is used to obtain the numerical solutions for the growth rate equations.

Keywords: Asymptotical stable, Commensal, Equilibrium state, Host, Liapunov's function, Neutral.

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1. Introduction

The positive and negative interactions between the species in question may be better understood with the use of mathematical modelling. The basic ideas of modelling in

biological science were presented by a number of writers, including Ma [6], Moghadas [7], Murray [8], and Sze-Bi Hsu [22]. Srinivas [21] investigated two- and three-species competitive ecosystems with finite and infinite resources, respectively. A number of mathematical models of ecological commensalism were also investigated by Kumar [5]. Prasad [9–19] examined two, three, and four species syn-ecosystems using continuous and discrete models. Gillman [3] and Kot [4] have both covered substantial ground in theoretical ecological research. This field owes a debt of gratitude to the work of several mathematicians and ecologists. The works of Anna Sher [1], Arumugam [2] and Sharma [20] outline the two primary branches of mathematical ecology, Autecology and Synecology, respectively. A syn-ecology is a kind of environment in which two or more different species coexist. All species engage in some kind of interaction with one another. Ammensalism, competition, commensalism, neutralism, mutualism, parasitism, predation, and so on are some of the ecological interactions.

2. In a commensalistic relationship, one group (S_1) benefits from another (S_2) without suffering any negative consequences or negative effects of its own. One species, S_1 , is known as the commensal, while the other, S_2 , is known as the host. Down below, you'll find a few instances of commensalism put into practice.

i. An oak tree provides shelter and food for a squirrel, but the tree itself does not gain or suffer any damage.

ii) A flatworm parasitizing a horse crab and consuming its food without harming the crab in any way.

3. Notation

S_1 : Commensal of S_2, S_3

S_2, S_3 : Host of S_1

$x_i(t)$: Population strength of S_i at time $t, i = 1, 2, 3$

t : Time instant

a_i : Natural growth rate of $S_i, i = 1, 2, 3$

a_{ii} : Self inhibition coefficients of $S_i, i = 1, 2, 3$

a_{12}, a_{13} : Interaction coefficients of S_1 due to S_2 and S_1 due to S_3

$k_i = \frac{a_i}{a_{ii}}$: Carrying capacities of $S_i, i = 1, 2, 3$

Further the variables x_1, x_2, x_3 are non-negative and the model parameters $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_{11}, a_{22}, a_{33}, a_{12}, a_{13}, k_1, k_2, k_3$ are assumed to be non-negative constants.

4. Basic Equations

Using this system of first-order non-linear ordinary differential equations, we can predict the ecology of the three species.

In a neutralist society, people of different backgrounds never communicate with one another. It's possible for different species to coexist in the same environment without ever having met, and they certainly aren't hurting or helping one another. Below, you can find a few instances from actual life.

i. The relationship between mountain valley dandelions and rainbow trout.

ii. Countless microbes that operate as residents in various human organs, including the skin, nose, mouth, etc.

Equation for the first species (x_1):

$$\frac{dx_1}{dt} = (a_{11} - a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3)x_1 \quad (1)$$

Equation for the second and third species (x_2 and x_3):

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = (a_{ii} - a_{ii}x_i)x_i, \quad i = 2, 3 \quad (2)$$

5. Equilibrium States

The system under investigation has eight equilibrium states given by

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

Fully washed out state.

$$c_1 : \bar{x}_1 = 0, \bar{x}_2 = 0, \bar{x}_3 = 0$$

States in which only two of the tree species are washed out while the other one is not.

$$c_2 : \bar{x}_1 = k_1, \bar{x}_2 = 0, \bar{x}_3 = 0$$

$$c_3 : \bar{x}_1 = 0, \bar{x}_2 = k_2, \bar{x}_3 = 0$$

$$c_4 : \bar{x}_1 = 0, \bar{x}_2 = 0, \bar{x}_3 = k_3$$

States in which only one of the tree species is washed out while the other two are not.

$$c_5 : \bar{x}_1 = k_1 + \frac{a_{12}k_2}{a_{11}}, \bar{x}_2 = k_2, \bar{x}_3 = 0$$

$$c_6 : \bar{x}_1 = k_1 + \frac{a_{13}k_3}{a_{11}}, \bar{x}_2 = 0, \bar{x}_3 = k_3$$

$$c_7 : \bar{x}_1 = 0, \bar{x}_2 = k_2, \bar{x}_3 = k_3$$

The co-existent state (or) normal steady state.

$$c_8 : \bar{x}_1 = k_1 + \frac{a_{12}k_2 + a_{13}k_3}{a_{11}}, \bar{x}_2 = k_2, \bar{x}_3 = k_3$$

6. Liapunov’s Function for Global Stability

The present corresponding author Prasad discussed earlier [9] the local stability of all above eight equilibrium states. From which only the normal steady state was found to be **stable** and rest of them **unstable**. In the present paper, the global stability of dynamical system (1) and (2) at this equilibrium state is examined by suitable Liapunov’s function.

Theorem : *The equilibrium state $c_8(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ is globally asymptotically stable.*

Proof: Let us consider the following Liapunov’s function for three species

$$L(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1 - x_1 \ln \left(\frac{x_1}{\bar{x}_1} \right) + l_1 \left[x_2 - x_2 \ln \left(\frac{x_2}{\bar{x}_2} \right) \right] + l_2 \left[x_3 - x_3 \ln \left(\frac{x_3}{\bar{x}_3} \right) \right] \tag{4}$$

where l_1 and l_2 are positive constants, to be chosen suitably

Now, the time derivative of L, along with solutions of (1) and (2) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \left(\frac{x_1 - x_1}{x_1} \right) \frac{dx_1}{dt} + l_1 \left(\frac{x_2 - x_2}{x_2} \right) \frac{dx_2}{dt} + l_2 \left(\frac{x_3 - x_3}{x_3} \right) \frac{dx_3}{dt} \tag{5} \\ &= (x_1 - \bar{x}_1)(a_{11} - a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + a_{13}x_3) + l_1(x_2 - \bar{x}_2)(a_{21} - a_{22}x_2) + l_2(x_3 - \bar{x}_3)(a_{31} - a_{33}x_3) \\ &= - \left[a_{11} (x_1 - \bar{x}_1) + a_{12} (x_1 - \bar{x}_1)(x_2 - \bar{x}_2) + a_{13} (x_1 - \bar{x}_1)(x_3 - \bar{x}_3) \right] + (x_2 - \bar{x}_2) \left[a_{21} (x_2 - \bar{x}_2) + a_{22} (x_2 - \bar{x}_2)^2 \right] \\ &\quad + (x_3 - \bar{x}_3) \left[a_{31} (x_3 - \bar{x}_3) + a_{33} (x_3 - \bar{x}_3)^2 \right] \end{aligned}$$

Choosing $l_1 = \frac{a_{12}^2}{4a_{11}a_{22}} > 0$, $l_2 = \frac{a_{13}^2}{4a_{11}a_{33}} > 0$ and with some algebraic manipulation, we get

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = - \sqrt{a_{11}} \left[(x_1 - \bar{x}_1) + \frac{a_{12}}{2a_{22}} (x_2 - \bar{x}_2) + \frac{a_{13}}{2a_{33}} (x_3 - \bar{x}_3) \right]^2 < 0 \text{ when } x_2 + x_3 < x_3 + x_2 \tag{6}$$

Hence, the steady state is **globally asymptotically stable**.

7. A Numerical Approach of the Growth Rate Equations

The numerical solutions of the growth rate equations (1) and (2) computed employing the fourth order Runge-Kutta method for specific values of the various parameters that characterize the model and the initial conditions. The results are illustrated in Figures 1 to 4.

Figure 1. Variation of x_1 , x_2 and x_3 against time (t) for $a_1=0.76$, $a_2=2.58$, $a_3=3.31$, $a_{11}=1.19$, $a_{22}=1.89$, $a_{33}=1.32$, $a_{12}=1.42$, $a_{13}=0.36$, $x_{10}=0.49$, $x_{20}=0.21$, $x_{30}=0.87$.

Figure 2. Variation of x_1 , x_2 and x_3 against time (t) for $a_1=0.53$, $a_2=1.06$, $a_3=0.23$, $a_{11}=0.07$, $a_{22}=0.13$, $a_{33}=0.23$, $a_{12}=0.1$, $a_{13}=0.63$, $x_{10}=2.6$, $x_{20}=1.67$, $x_{30}=1.04$.

Figure 3. Variation of x_1 , x_2 and x_3 against time (t) for $a_1=0.351$, $a_2=0.468$, $a_3=0.288$, $a_{11}=1.341$, $a_{22}=1.341$, $a_{33}=0.378$, $a_{12}=0.351$, $a_{13}=0.144$, $x_{10}=x_{20}=x_{30}=4$.

Figure 4. Variation of x_1 , x_2 and x_3 against time (t) for $a_1=0.36$, $a_2=0.544$, $a_3=0.464$, $a_{11}=0.208$, $a_{22}=0.208$, $a_{33}=0.832$, $a_{12}=0.776$, $a_{13}=0.232$, $x_{10}=0.704$, $x_{20}=0.464$, $x_{30}=0.896$.

8. Observations & Conclusions

Observations of the numerical solutions

Case 1: In this case the initial conditions of S_2 , S_1 , S_3 are in increasing order and the natural growth rate of S_3 is highest. Initially the third species dominates over the first species up to the time instant $t^* = 1.63$ after which the dominance is reversed as shown in Figure 1.

Case 2: The first species dominates over the other two throughout. In this the third species is a weak competitor with no appreciable

Case 4: Initially the third species dominates over the second till the time instant $t^* = 2.5$ and thereafter the dominance is reversed. Also the first species dominates over the second till the time instant $t^* = 0.17$ and the dominance gets reversed thereafter. This is illustrated in Figure 4.

In the present work, we discussed on the global stability of ecological three species consisting of host, commensal and neutralism with growth rates. In this paper we established all possible equilibrium states and the global stability is established with the help of suitable Liapunov's

growth even from the start. Further the third species with low natural birth rate. (Figure 2).

Case 3: In this case the initial conditions of the three species are identical. It is evident that all the three species asymptotically converge to the equilibrium point. Further we notice that the selfinhibition coefficients of first and second species are same. This is shown in Figure 3.

function for only the normal steady state. Further, the growth rates of the species are numerically estimated using Runge-Kutta fourth order method in four cases.

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